

TYPES OF PHRASEOLOGISMS AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *In this article, while studying the unique features of phraseological units in the English and Uzbek languages, their comparative-typological analysis is carried out.*

Key words: *phraseological units, phraseologism, stable word combinations, synonymy.*

A phraseological unit is a unit related to language and speech as a linguistic phenomenon. A linguistic unit consisting of the combination of more than one independent lexeme and having a figurative and spiritual nature is called a phraseological unit: ‘the hair on the top is standing up, the vinegar does not raise water; to show the white feather, to play the first fiddle’.

Phraseological unit is also referred to as phrase, phraseologism, stable compound, stable compound, phraseological compound.

The following are the main signs of phraseological units:

1. Two or more lexemes are part of the phraseological unit.
2. Phraseological unit represents a single lexical meaning.
3. The words in the phraseological unit have lost their lexical meaning.
4. Phraseological unit as a stable combination with a free combination is only in the homonymic state.
5. A phraseological unit can be replaced only as a whole
6. Phraseological unit comes in a syntactic function as a whole in the structure of the sentence.
7. A phraseological unit cannot be translated into another language word for word, it is translated as a whole. [1]

According to the constituent of a phraseological unit, a compound lexeme is similar to a phrase and a sentence. However, they live more ready and stable in the mind of the language community, like a joint lexeme. In other words, the phraseological unit has the nature of generality characteristic of all linguistic units in the language and appears as a feature in the speech. So, a phraseological combination is not a speech

event, but a language event. Also, the phraseological unit has a nominative meaning, so it is put on the same line as the lexeme, and it is called a nominative unit larger than the lexeme.

Two phenomena are distinguished in the content plan of phraseological units: 1) lexical meaning, more precisely, phraseological meaning; 2) methodological assessment. The meaning of a constituent morpheme, lexeme is usually embodied as a sum of meanings specific to the language units that make it up, and the meaning of the whole is understood based on the meaning of the parts. A phraseological unit is a linguistic unit, but its meaning is not equal to the simple sum of the meanings inherent in lexemes. In relation to the meaning of the lexemes in the meaning of phraseological units, the denominator is embodied as a superlative meaning, which may not depend on the meaning of the lexemes in the meaning. Due to the fact that the meaning of phraseological units is not a simple sum of the meanings specific to lexemes, but a new meaning built on top of them, there seems to be a break between the plan of expression and the plan of content in phraseological units. Specific meanings do not directly explain the general meaning. Therefore, the connection between the plan of expression and the plan of content in phraseological units becomes conditional. Here, more than one word as a whole undergoes semantic development based on a certain image, by means of transfer. Such a superimposed figurative meaning based on a certain image is called a phraseological meaning.[1.2]

By studying the semantic properties of phraseological units, it was determined that they contain phraseological polysemy, phraseological synonymy, phraseological antonymy, phraseological homonymy and paronymy phenomena [1].

Phraseological synonymy - synonymy is one of the semantic microsystems between language units, and also among phraseological units. In order to call two phraseological units synonymous, they must have the same meaning. Without it, it is impossible to talk about synonymy. It is not appropriate to understand the same meaning as the same meaning. Each synonym has its own edge of meaning, in addition to the general meaning of this nest of synonymy. Synonyms usually differ in one or more ways, one of which may be a difference in meaning. For example, to be in a bad mood and to be down in the mouth are synonyms of the phraseological unit: to be in a bad mood and to be down in the mouth. These synonyms, regardless of their other characteristics, differ in terms of meaning: in the latter, the meaning is somewhat stronger. When defining phraseological synonyms, the basis of another image is also taken into account. For example, a mouth, a shingle, a pinch of synonym phraseological units are based on various images: the organ of speech, a part of a head of grapes, the amount to be pinched.

Synonymous phraseological units should be distinguished from variants of one phraseological unit. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the word-components of phraseological units. There is no doubt that phraseological units that do not have the same word-component in the lexicon are synonyms. For example, from thread to needle, mirid to secret, from hair to tail, which means "in every detail, to the smallest detail", is a mutual synonym of the phraseological unit, and they do not have a common word-component [2].

Synonymy is a phenomenon defined on the basis of meaning. The same ambiguity is determined between phrases in monosemantic phraseological units. If a polysemantic phraseological unit participates in a synonymous relationship, it should be derived not from a phraseological unit, but from a concrete phraseological meaning.

Phraseological antonymy. Antonymy is one of the phenomena determined on the basis of the semantic relationship between language units, and it is also found in phraseological units at the level of words. Determining antonymy, on the one hand, leads to a deeper understanding of the lexical meaning of phraseological units, on the other hand, it helps to distinguish between the meanings of one phrase in polysemy, and on the third hand, it is useful in defining synonyms.

In short, phraseological units in each language have their own linguistic features. But in all languages, phraseological units serve as language wealth. Polysemantic phraseological units serve to enrich the lexical structure of the language and speech and embody the meanings of emotional coloring.

Phraseological units play an incomparable role in conveying the uniqueness, lifestyle, material and spiritual values, history, culture, and customs of the peoples of the world into their own language. Phraseological units are related to how individuals use language units, as well as the basic rules and language norms that regulate their use. Use of phraseological units in speech, translation of their use in terms of national-cultural universality, differential and paradigmatic features, ways of transition from folk oral creativity to literary language, semantic features, artistic-stylistic possibilities, form and meaning explanation in terms of problems. , the importance of elucidating their place in the national language, the necessity of a dictionary suitable for modern linguistics is presented. Speaking about the contextual features of phraseological units, it can be said that there is a classification of phraseological structures according to the context, which are designated as phraseomes and idioms.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Contextual features reflecting this type of phraseological units were first distinguished by Professor A.V. Kunin. Phraseological and phraseological units are

distinguished from free word combinations and compound words by their phraseological stability.

The theory of stability was also developed by Professor A. V. Kunin. A.V. Kunin considers sustainability as a multifaceted concept that includes the following elements:

1. Consistency of Use. This shows that phraseological units are not formed in speech, but are repeated in a ready form.

2. Lexical stagnation means that phraseological units cannot be replaced (for example, red tape, and mare's nest) or partially replaced within the framework of phraseological variation: lexical (skeleton in the closet - skeleton in the closet, blind pig. - blind or yo'lbars), grammatical (stone heart - stone heart), positional and mixed options.

3. Lexical stability of phraseological units is used to determine semantic stability. The meaning of the phraseological unit is preserved despite minor changes. It can only be identified, clarified, reduced or enhanced.

4. Syntactic consistency.

According to Kunin, any phraseology that does not have one of these stagnation qualities cannot be considered a phraseological unit. In this regard, there is a question of translating English idioms into another language, which have only idioms as a unique feature, and have a unique, unbroken phraseological structure. Preserving the lexical, semantic and linguistic features of idioms is a very difficult task. From the point of view of genetics, it is known that the structure of the English language differs from the structure of the Uzbek language; they belong to separate

language families. As a result, the grammatical structures of different languages differ from each other. There are several affixes in the Uzbek language, for example; the phrase begins with a noun and ends with a verb; there are no prepositions, articles, or gender categories. English has articles, prepositions and affixes. As a result, trying to translate words, phrases, sentences and especially idioms presents some difficulties. Moreover, the differences in form and meaning between English and Uzbek idioms make translation problematic. For example, — *hot under the collar* if translated as —yoqa ostidagi issiqlik ..., —*tepa sochi tikka bo'ldi* is the Uzbek version of this phrase. As can be seen from the example, the difficulty in mastering idioms is related to the disparity in terms of form and meaning. It should be noted that translating idioms from English to another language is very difficult. Because most of them are bright, inventive, laconic and vague, it is so. In translation, it is important not only to express the content of the phrase, but also to show its figurativeness, keeping in mind the methodological goal. When translating idioms, the translator must find an equivalent term in the local language and convey their meaning and imagery while preserving the

stylistic function of idioms. If there is no equivalent representation in the local language, the translator is forced to settle for an "approximate match.

CONCLUSION

Distinctions in semantic and stylistic tasks performed by words with the same real meaning in different languages, as well as differences in the combinations of such words in different languages, are extremely important for both practice and translation theory. They often cause great practical difficulties and are of great theoretical interest, because they differ in the semantic and stylistic functions of words with the same real meaning in different languages, and the way such words enter different languages.

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